

Understanding the insertion/folding mechanism of penetratin for specific lipid compositions

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Abstract

Penetratin is a cationic peptide able to enter cells by direct membrane translocation. This cell-penetrating peptide strongly interacts with anionic lipids and can fold into an alpha-helix in the contact of anionic lipid membranes. We have characterised by temperature replica-exchange molecular dynamics (T-REMD) the completed insertion / folding mechanism of penetratin in membranes of different lipid compositions: a membrane made of anionic lipids (DMPG) to which penetratin binds with strong affinity, and a membrane made of zwitterionic lipids (DMPC) to which penetratin binds only weakly. Extensive T-REMD simulations in water and in the two lipid compositions were compared with experimental CD and NMR data. In water, both simulations and experiments agree revealing about 20% of helix. The T-REMD simulations in lipids are slow at converging but they display the right experimental trends. In DMPG, the peptide inserts and folds within the membrane / water interface. Once folded, the alpha-helix is stable. This is consistent with CD experiments published in literature. In DMPC, the peptide has less affinity and possibly unbinds from the membrane. However, a few replicas display some transient helical states, which are confirmed by NMR transferred NOE experiments. These helical states are not easily detectable from the CD experiments since the signal is largely dominated by unstructured conformations. The simulations also reveal the key role of the consecutive IWF residues of penetratin. By partitioning deeply in the membrane hydrophobic core, they act as a kinetic trap impairing helix folding in DMPG, or penetratin unbinding in DMPC. Overall, T-REMD is a very useful technique, next to biophysical experiments such as NMR and CD, to understand the fine molecular interactions between membrane peptides and lipids.

Introduction

Membrane active or membranotropic peptides are ubiquitous peptides that directly interact with biological membranes [1, 2] and have important biological functions. For example, many antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) kill bacteria by a variety of mechanisms such as toroidal pores or detergent effect [3], leading to membrane permeabilisation [4]. Cell-penetrating peptides (CPPs) are another class of membrane-active peptides capable of entering cells without damaging the plasma membrane [5, 6, 7]. CPPs are promising molecules in the field of drug delivery since they can carry a cargo (e.g. another peptide, an oligonucleotide or a drug) across the cell membranes [8, 9]. To understand the mechanisms of action of these peptides, it is important to combine a variety of experimental and computational methods that probe from the cellular to the molecular scale [2].

A large number of AMPs and CPPs are amphipathic helices (AH), that are unfolded in solution but fold into an alpha-helix upon membrane binding. The helix is oriented parallel to the membrane surface and inserts in the membrane / water interface, thus they are sometimes called interfacial peptides [10]. This positioning allows them to have their hydrophobic side facing the membrane interior and their hydrophilic side facing the lipid polar heads / water environment, while forming intra-helical hydrogen bonds which are energetically favourable. The thermodynamics of AH / membrane interaction is now well known [10, 11]. White and collaborators describe this as the partitioning / folding coupling [10], meaning that both processes are coupled. White also insists on the fact that the binding of an AH to

a membrane should be viewed as a partitioning process since a bilayer contains multiple binding sites. The thermodynamics of this process can be conveniently evaluated with a variety of experimental methods such as titrations using circular dichroism, fluorescence spectroscopy [10], or isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) [11]. In 2012, it was proposed that each helical residue contributes (additively) -0.37 kcal mol⁻¹ to the overall free energy of partitioning [12]. Another important feature of AH partitioning, revealed by X-ray diffraction, is that their centre of mass stands at the glycerol level [13]. This implies that they undergo a membrane insertion since they have to go below the "crowded phosphate level".

Next to biophysical experiments, computational methods are crucial to help interpret indirect experimental observations at the molecular scale [14, 15]. Many all-atom computational studies revealed useful insights on AH partitioning / folding mechanism. Most of the time, enhanced sampling methods had to be used in order to observe these phenomena that are usually too slow for regular molecular dynamics (MD) at room temperature [16, 17]. T-REMD (temperature replica-exchange molecular dynamics) was one of the first enhanced technique used to study the insertion / folding of the WALP16 transmembrane peptide [18]. One advantage of T-REMD is that there is no need to choose a reaction coordinate that may bias the observations. Due to the limited computational power at that time (3.5 ns per replica), extreme temperatures had to be used up to 800 K, requiring the use of position restraints on lipids to avoid membrane explosion. A more recent study addressed the insertion / folding of the A β 10-40 peptide using a more reasonable temperature range up to 430 K [19]. In these conditions, the bilayer remained intact. Cui et al. used metadynamics to probe how the H0 helix of endophilin senses membrane curvature [20]. More recently, metadynamics has also been applied to study the interaction of epsin AH (a cytoskeletal protein) with membranes [21]. Chen et al. took advantage of the thermostability of the melittin AMP to conduct high temperature MD simulations which allowed them to observe its complete insertion followed by its folding in the membrane / water interface [22]. Using umbrella sampling (US) simulations, some studies on the transportan (TP10) peptide, which is not strictly amphipathic, could evaluate how it passes from a transmembrane to an interfacial state [23, 24]. US has also been used to study penetratin and TP10 translocation process with a special reaction coordinate (i.e. the partitioning of hydrophobic residues) [25]. Overall, US gives access to the free energy of insertion but it is difficult to take into account the folding of the peptide (usually the peptide is kept folded on each window along the vertical axis). Replica exchange with solute tempering (REST 2) has been used to study the binding of the peptide PGLa at low [19] and high [26] peptide to lipid (P/L) ratio. It was possible to observe not only the peptide insertion and folding but also its dimerisation at high P/L ratio. In the REST 2 technique, only the solute is heated by mimicking a raise of temperature via a change of hamiltonian.

Penetratin is a 16-residue peptide derived from the Antennapedia homeodomain (Antp) of *Drosophila* [27]. It has the remarkable property to directly translocate across plasma membranes, being one of the first CPPs to be discovered. As the major DNA-binding site within homeodomain, penetratin sequence contains 3 Arg and 4 Lys basic residues, conferring a high positive charge. Thus penetratin was shown to strongly interact *in vitro* with membranes containing negatively charged lipids [28, 29]. These electrostatic interactions not only contribute to enhance membrane affinity but are also thought to be directly involved in the translocation mechanism [30, 31]. An *in vitro* study using droplet interface bilayers showed that it translocates across negatively charged membranes made of palmitoylphosphatidylglycerol (POPG), but not across palmitoylphosphatidylcholine (POPC) [32]. Penetratin structure was solved by solution NMR in different anionic membrane-mimicking environments (SDS micelles, lipid bicelles) [33, 34, 35, 36] and was shown to adopt an α -helix [34]. Like most AH, penetratin is unfolded in solution and folded in the membrane / water interface [10]. Indeed, circular dichroism (CD) revealed that it has a random coil conformation in solution but there is a net formation of α -helix in the presence of negatively charged membranes made of dimyristoylphosphatidylglycerol (DMPG) [29]. In the presence of zwitterionic membranes made of dimyristoylphosphatidylcholine (DMPC), the CD spectrum was almost identical to that in buffer [29], hinting at first that there would not be any binding to that composition. However, the picture is slightly more complicated, since it was shown in the same study by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) that the peptide has weak interactions with DMPC lipids (i.e. slight decrease of the cooperativity of the gel to fluid transition) [29]. This observation questions the molecular details of these weak interactions, and what the conformations of penetratin during these slight encounters are. Does the peptide remain unfolded at all times or may it form some reversible helix?

As described above, we have a rather good view of AH / membrane interactions thanks to all the experimental and computational studies. However, some questions remain, such as a better understanding of the fine peptide / membrane interactions controlling lipid specificity. Many simulation studies pub-

lished in the literature focused on a peptide that binds to a specific lipid composition. But what happens exactly when a peptide binds weakly to another composition? It is also interesting to assess whether the computational techniques and available peptide / membrane force fields are able to capture such fine details. To answer these questions, we studied penetratin using extensive T-REMD simulations in water and in two lipid compositions: DMPC in which it is hypothesized to weakly bind and DMPG in which it has strong binding affinity. Regarding the simulations in lipids, two starting structures were used. The first was unfolded in solution away from the bilayer, the second was folded in an α -helix and embedded within the membrane / water interface. Some replicas of the T-REMD simulations reproduce the experimental observations and give a complete molecular view of important processes: full insertion and folding of penetratin in DMPG, and unbinding from the membrane in DMPC. Interestingly, penetratin does interact with DMPC polar heads (notably via Trp 48 and Phe 49) even though it does not bind strongly to this composition. Transferred NOE NMR experiments confirm this transient membrane interaction by revealing a weakly populated helical state (less than 5 %). Overall our work gives a better view of peptide folding and interaction with membranes of different lipid compositions. It also confirms the robustness of CHARMM36 force field to describe peptide conformational space and peptide/membrane interactions.

Materials and Methods

Molecular dynamics methods

Penetratin model

Here, the NMR structure resolved by Lindberg et al. [34] (PDB code: **1OMQ**) was used as a starting structure for the *IN* and *Water* systems (Figure 1 and Table 1). Among the ensemble of 20 NMR structures, the first model was chosen as it is the most representative. This structure was determined at 310 K in a bicelle of (DMPC/DMPG)/DHPC (90:10) $q=0.5$ (long chain to short chain lipid ratio). Under these conditions, the structure is an α -helix on the segment from tryptophan 48 (W48) to arginine 53 (R53) in more than 40% of the 20 structures (and more than 80% on the F49-R52 portion). The C-terminal residue was amidated in order to maximise its positive charges.

System compositions

The three types of systems presented below for this study were constructed using either GROMACS version 2022.5 [37] or the online tool CHARMM-GUI [38].

All the system compositions are summarised in Table 1. It is important to note that the starting structure of penetratin in the '*OUT*' systems (*OUT*_{DMPC} and *OUT*_{DMPG}) is extracted from the 'Water' simulation between 200 and 500 ns as the most representative conformation using the GROMOS clustering method [39] with a cut-off of 0.4 nm (See Figure S2 for the structure).

Figure 1: Starting structure for each simulation. A) in Water with penetratin folded. B) folded and inserted inside the membrane. C) unfolded outside the membrane (this structure is shown in S2). Penetratin is represented in cyan *new cartoon*, the membrane is represented in sticks coloured by atom type (carbon: cyan, oxygen: red, hydrogen: white, nitrogen: blue and phosphorus: tan) and the water (TIP3P) is represented in sticks coloured by atom [40].

Name	<i>Water</i>	<i>IN</i> _{DMPC}	<i>IN</i> _{DMPG}	<i>OUT</i> _{DMPC}	<i>OUT</i> _{DMPG}
Starting structure	Figure 1.A	Figure 1.B		Figure 1.C	
Box type	rhombic dodecahedron	parallelepiped			
Number of lipids	0	100 DMPC	100 DMPG	100 DMPC	100 DMPG
Penetratin's position	1 nm from the edges	glycerol level of the upper leaflet		1.5 nm from the upper leaflet	
Penetratin's structure		folded		unfolded	
Number of water molecules (TIP3P) [41]	3,991	4,000	4,000	4,000	4,000
Ion concentration	150 mM				
Number of ions	12 Na ⁺ 20 Cl ⁻	17 Na ⁺ 9 Cl ⁻	101 Na ⁺ 9 Cl ⁻	17 Na ⁺ 9 Cl ⁻	101 Na ⁺ 9 Cl ⁻
Number of atoms	12,341	24,162	23,546	24,162	23,546

Table 1: Starting structure and box composition of the 5 different systems presented. The complete name of the lipid is 1,2-dimyristoylphosphatidylcholine for DMPC and 1,2-dimyristoylphosphatidylglycerol for DMPG.

Force field and MD parameters

All molecular dynamics (MD) simulations were performed using GROMACS 2022.5 [37] and the CHARMM36 lipid force field [42] and CHARMM36m peptide force field [43]. Temperature replica exchange molecular dynamics (T-REMD) [44, 45] was generally used, except for pure membrane simulations. For all simulations, the Leap Frog algorithm [46] was used, the bonds involving hydrogen atoms were kept rigid using the LINCS algorithm [47] allowing a time step of 2 fs. Non-bonded interactions were cut off at 1.2 nm and a force switch was used to gently bring the value to 0 from 1.0 nm. PME [48, 49] was used to take into account electrostatic interactions beyond the cut-off.

Each system was first minimised using a steepest descent algorithm [50] and then equilibrated in 6 phases using the CHARMM-GUI [38] protocol. First in the NVT ensemble and then in the NPT ensemble. The desired temperature was set to 310 K using a velocity-rescale thermostat [51]. The pressure

was controlled by a cell-rescale barostat [52] and maintained at 1 bar semi-isotropically. During the six equilibration phases, position restraints were used and gently removed. For the protein backbone the position restraints were (in kJ/mol/nm²): 4000.0, 2000.0, 1000.0, 500.0, 200.0 and 50.0. For the protein side chains, they were: 2000.0, 1000.0, 500.0, 200.0, 50.0 and 0.0. For the lipids, they were: 1000.0, 400.0, 400.0, 200.0, 40.0 and 0.0.

The Temperature generator for REMD-simulations [53] was used to predict the temperatures for each T-REMD simulation. The bottom temperature was chosen at 310 K so that it was above the gel to fluid phase transition temperature of DMPC and DMPG. The maximum temperature was set to 412 K, high enough to pass free energy barriers, but not too high to ensure membrane integrity. An exchange probability of 0.2 was used. Each T-REMD was run using the standard protocol [44, 45] as implemented in GROMACS [37]. Each replica was first thermalised using standard MD for each temperature before proceeding to the T-REMD production simulations. 33 replicas were used for the T-REMD of penetratin in water (*Water*) and 38 for the systems with membranes (The list of the temperatures can be found in Table S1). Exchanges were attempted every 10 ps between neighbouring replicas. T-REMD [44, 45] in water and those with penetratin inserted into the membrane (*Water* and *IN* systems) were run for 500 ns, while the T-REMD with the peptide outside the membrane of DMPC (*OUT_{DMPC}*) were run for 1 μ s and the one with the peptide outside the membrane of DMPG (*OUT_{DMPG}*) were run for 2.3 μ s. Most analyses were made on the second half of the simulations (250-500 for 500 ns simulations and 500-1000 for 1 000 ns simulations) except for the *OUT_{DMPG}*, which were made between 500 and 2 374 ns. All simulation visualisation were made with Visual molecular dynamics (VMD) software [40].

Systems containing lipids (either DMPC or DMPG) with water (TIP3P [41]) were also constructed. These systems contain 256 lipids, 40 TIP3P water per lipid (full hydration) and 150 mM NaCl. They were also minimised using a steepest descent algorithm [50] and equilibrated in 6 phases using the CHARMM-GUI [38] protocol (2 in the NVT ensemble and 4 in the NPT ensemble). The desired temperature was set to 310 K using a Berendsen thermostat [?] during equilibration and a velocity-rescale thermostat [51] for the production. The pressure was maintained at 1 bar semi-isotropically by a Berendsen barostat [?] during equilibration and a cell-rescale barostat [52] during the production. During the equilibration phases, position restraints were used and gently removed. The lipids restraints were (in kJ/mol/nm²): 1000.0, 400.0, 400.0, 200.0, 40.0 and 0.0.

Experimental Methods

Materials

Penetratin peptide (sequence ₄₃RQIKIWFQNRRMKWKK₅₈-NH₂, corresponding to Antennapedia homeodomain third helix) was synthesized using Fmoc solid-phase peptide synthesis and purified by reverse phase HPLC at the peptide synthesis platform of IBPS, Sorbonne Université. Lipids were purchased from Avanti Polar Lipids (Alabaster, AL, USA).

CD spectroscopy

CD spectra were recorded on a Jasco J-815 spectropolarimeter. Ellipticity measurements were carried out at 37 °C using a quartz cell of 1 mm path length. Spectra were recorded from 190 to 270 nm, with a bandwidth of 1 nm, a step size of 0.2 nm and a scanning speed of 20 nm min⁻¹, and were averaged over 4 scans. CD samples were prepared in 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 6.5, using a peptide concentration of 50 μ M. CD spectra were processed with R software.

NMR spectroscopy

All NMR experiments were recorded on a Bruker Avance NEO 600 MHz spectrometer equipped with a ¹H/¹⁹F/¹³C/¹⁵N QCI cryoprobe. Experiments were processed with Bruker TopSpin 4.3 program and analysed with NMRFAM-SPARKY. NMR samples were prepared in 5 mm Shigemi tubes using a volume of 300 μ L of 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 6.5, 91/9 (v/v) H₂O/D₂O. Peptide concentrations were 1 mM in the absence of lipids, and 0.5 mM in the presence of 12.9 mM POPC SUVs. NMR experiments on penetratin peptide were recorded between 5 °C and 30 °C. ¹H, ¹³C, ¹⁵N resonance were assigned from the analysis of 2D ¹H-¹H TOCSY, 2D ¹H-¹H NOESY, 2D ¹H-¹³C HSQC, 2D ¹H-¹³C HSQC-TOCSY, and 2D ¹H-¹⁵N HSQC spectra. Chemical shifts were referenced to DSS. NMR experiments on penetratin peptide in the presence of POPC SUVs were recorded at 20 °C and 30 °C. 2D NOESY experiments were

recorded with similar acquisition parameters in the absence and in the presence of lipids (150 ms mixing time).

Results

Simulations of penetratin in water reveal mostly unfolded conformations

We first assessed the conformations of penetratin in *Water* using T-REMD simulations. Figure 2 shows the amount of helix along each replica, represented by a colour scale (from black to yellow). Since the starting conformation was a full alpha-helix, the yellow colour is present at the beginning but rapidly fades to dark as the T-REMD progresses for almost all replicas. The average helicity across all replicas takes approximately 250 ns to converge and reaches around 10 % (Figure S1). After 250 ns, the amount of helix remains very low for all replicas except replicas 23 and 31. This is perfectly consistent with CD experiments [29], NMR data (see below) and the overall behaviour of AH in water buffer [10]. The analysis per residue shows that this residual helicity mainly spans I47 to Q50 (Figure S3-A).

Figure 2: Helicity of the 33 replicas of the *Water* system during the 500 ns T-REMD simulation. The more yellow the colour, the more helical the peptide. Note that each replica diffuses in temperature but each trajectory is continuous.

Simulations of membrane-inserted alpha-helical penetratin show different stability according to lipid composition

Penetratin is known to form an alpha-helix in negatively charged membranes and to have weak interactions with zwitterionic membranes [29]. Even if penetratin remains essentially unfolded in the presence of zwitterionic membranes, the weak membrane interactions may be compatible with transient alpha-helix formation [54]. Prompted by these observations, we assessed the alpha-helix stability in both negatively charged lipids (DMPG) and zwitterionic lipids (DMPC) using again T-REMD (Figure 3). It was particularly important to use an enhanced sampling technique since conformational changes are severely slowed down in a membrane medium compared to liquid water. We name these simulations *IN* since the starting conformation is penetratin embedded in the membrane.

Figure 3-A shows the evolution of helicity for the system IN_{DMPG} . The peptide remains embedded in the bilayer at all times for all replicas. Since the starting conformation is an alpha-helix (the NMR structure [34]), the first 200 ns display a high helical content which gradually decreases after 300 ns, as shown by mixed colours (violet / orange / yellow). The helix content stabilises to 60 % (see also Figure S1). All replicas remain somehow fully or partially helical, except replica 22 which fully unfolds but reversibly at the near end of the simulation. The helicity per residue in the second half of the simulation is above

90 % from I45 to R52 (and almost 100 % for segment W48-N51) (Figure S3-B). Overall, the T-REMD predicts a rather stable alpha-helix. However, at this stage, the T-REMD has not fully converged and it appears likely that the mean helical content could continue to decrease if we prolonged the simulation.

Figure 3: (A) Helicity of the 38 replicates of the IN_{DMPG} system during the 500 ns T-REMD. (B) Helicity of the 38 replicates of the IN_{DMPC} system during the 500 ns T-REMD. The more yellow the colour, the more helical the peptide. Note that each replica diffuses in temperature but each trajectory is continuous.

Figure 3-B shows the system IN_{DMPC} . Also here, the peptide remains in the bilayer at all times for all replicas. The first 50 ns are rich in alpha-helix (yellow colour) because of the starting structure, but as the T-REMD proceeds the situation is pretty different compared to DMPG. First, the highly helical conformations (yellow) disappear more rapidly, some already start to vanish before or around 100 ns (e.g. replicas 21 or 36). Second, after a few hundreds of ns, some replicas are completely unfolded (black) and never fold back into an alpha-helix (e.g. replicas 6, 19, 21, 36). The mean helicity over all replicas has not completely converged (Figure S1), but one can see the trend towards a decreasing amount of helix. We expect that if we prolonged the simulations, the mean helical content would continue to decrease. At this stage, these T-REMD simulations cannot definitely answer the question as to whether the alpha-helix may occur in DMPC, but they do tell this helical conformation is less stable than in DMPG. This can also be seen on the helicity per residue which is less important (around 80 % on the part I47-Q50) compared to DMPG (Figure S3-C).

Simulations started from penetratin outside of a DMPG membrane unveil the full insertion / folding mechanism

To get a detailed view of the complete insertion / folding coupling mechanism, we ran some simulations starting with the peptide outside of the membrane (named *OUT* simulations). The starting structure was obtained by clustering the conformations at the bottom temperature (310 K) of the Water T-REMD (see Methods and Figure S2). Note that this latter has a few residues in alpha-helix.

Figure 4 shows the system OUT_{DMPG} regarding the position of penetratin with respect to the membrane as well as its secondary structure. Driven by favourable electrostatic interactions, penetratin is rapidly attracted to the membrane and inserts into it within less than 50 ns (Figure 4-A). It then remains embedded within the membrane / water interface until the end of the simulation. Because the starting structure has a few residues in alpha-helical conformation, some frames in violet can be observed at the beginning (Figure 4-B). After 200 ns, the colour turns either to black (unfolded) for a majority of replicas or to orange / yellow (folded) for a few replicas (i.e. 5, 18, 19, 26 and 34). These latter thus present some complete folding of penetratin within the bilayer interface. Interestingly, we could observe that there was systematically a precise succession of events for these replica: i) rapid diffusion towards the membrane, ii) insertion of large hydrophobic / aromatic residues (as observed for example for the ALPS peptide [55]) and complete unfolding of the peptide if a few residues were initially helical, iii) folding within the interface. This could come somewhat as a surprise, but the peptide needs to be completely unfolded for the hydrophobic residues to be fully (deeply) inserted, and then interfacial folding can proceed. However, the full phenomenon is extremely slow and we could thus observe it only for a few replicas, even if we used T-REMD. The monitoring of the average helicity over all replicas (Figure S1) confirms these two observations: i) the average helicity after 1500 ns is less important than in water (below 10 %), ii) it hardly increases between 1500 and 2000 ns. This is due to the fact that only 5 out of 37 replicas (thus 13 % of them) have undergone folding, and way longer simulations would be needed to equilibrate the helical content over all replicas. Regarding penetratin partitioning, all large hydrophobic residues are fully inserted in the second half of T-REMD (Figure S4). However, the central I47, W48 and F49 residues are the most deeply buried. R52 and R53 are also quite buried and their side chain probably snorkel so that the guanidinium group can make salt bridge interactions with DMPG phosphate groups.

An example of the full process insertion / folding is shown in Figure 5. One can see that the N-terminal residue bearing two positive charges is first attracted (panels a to c) leading to a first "adsorption" (panel d) of the peptide on the membrane. Then the residual helix totally unfolds which allows the deep insertion of W48 and F49. Then helix folding proceeds from the N-terminus to the C-terminus (panels f to h) leading to a completely folded alpha-helix with all aromatic residues well buried within the hydrophobic core of the membrane. Note that the final alpha-helix is slightly tilted (N-terminus more buried than the C-terminus), which is in good agreement with experimental data [34]. It makes perfect sense since the second half of the peptide is rich in positively charged residues that prefer the polar heads / water compartment. Interestingly, all the replicas for which we observed full insertion / folding follow a similar succession of events.

Figure 4: Penetratin rapidly inserts in the DMPG membrane and eventually folds within the interface. (A) Minimum peptide / membrane distance for all replicas of the *OUT*_{DMPG} system. (B) Helicity of the 38 replicas of the *OUT*_{DMPG} system during the 2.3 μ s simulation. The more yellow the colour, the more helical the peptide. For both plots, each replica diffuses in temperature but each trajectory is continuous.

Figure 5: Full mechanism of insertion / folding of penetratin in a DMPG membrane from replicate 19. The peptide is shown in new cartoon representation and the membrane is drawn in lines. The alpha carbon of residue R43 is shown as a van der Waals sphere to pinpoint the N-terminus. The aromatic amino-acids (W48, F49 and W56) are drawn as orange licorice. (a) $t = 0$ ns; (b) $t = 0.1$ ns; (c) $t = 3.6$ ns; (d) $t = 4.7$ ns; (e) $t = 55$ ns; (f) $t = 125.9$ ns; (g) $t = 300.3$ ns; (h) $t = 603.3$ ns. Note that the box volume is changing significantly (see the edges represented as blue lines) because the replica is diffusing in temperature (the higher the temperature, the larger the area per lipid).

Simulations started from penetratin outside of a DMPC membrane reveal reversible weak binding events

Figure 6 shows the system OUT_{DMPC} regarding the position of penetratin with respect to the membrane as well as its secondary structure. The picture is completely different compared to DMPG. First, the diffusion towards the bilayer is much slower and reversible until 400 ns (Figure 6-A). This is due to the less favourable electrostatic interactions between penetratin and DMPC lipids. During this phase, we thus observe some complete unbinding events of penetratin from the DMPC bilayer. After 400 ns, all replicas are inserted and we no longer observe unbinding events. We explain this by the very strong anchoring driven by I47, W48 and F49. Once these three residues are deeply buried within the hydrophobic core, the cost of removing them from there is very high explaining why we do not observe this after 400 ns. Of course, this does not mean it could not occur. This can be well seen in the partitioning plot of the different amino-acids (Figure S4): only these 3 residues are deeply buried, the next ones in the sequence lie upper at the level of polar heads or in the water phase. For example, R52 and R53, which were quite buried in DMPG, are now at the level of phosphate groups and the guanidinium groups make more interactions with water.

Regarding secondary structures (Figure 6-B), many replicas totally unfold (black), but some form a partial helix (violet to orange), and 4 of them form a full helix (orange to yellow). However this folding is systemically reversible and lasts less long compared to the situation in DMPG. Moreover, the helix is systematically less buried. The folding in DMPC may appear as a surprise, thus it prompted us to check its existence using NMR and CD experiments (see next section).

Figure 6: Penetratin reversibly binds to DMPC membrane and remains essentially unfolded when inserted within the interface. (A) Minimum peptide / membrane distance for all replicas of the (A) *OUT_{DMPC}* system. (B) Helicity of the 38 replicates of the *OUT_{DMPC}* system during the 1 μ s simulation. The more yellow the colour, the more folded the peptide. For both plots, each replica diffuses in temperature but each trajectory is continuous.

An example of the full process of penetratin unbinding is shown in Figure 7. We start from an extended conformation with the three aromatic residues (W48, F49 and W56) moderately buried within the membrane hydrophobic core (panel a). F49 first unbinds from the membrane (panel b) followed by W56 (panel c). W48 is the last one to unbind allowing the peptide to definitely leave the membrane upper leaflet (panel d). Then, the peptide freely diffuses in the water compartment (panels e to g) and approaches the lower leaflet. Eventually, it proceeds with a new phase of insertion in that leaflet guided by its N-terminal part (panel h). Interestingly, all the replicas for which we observed full penetratin unbinding proceed in the same way.

Figure 7: Full mechanism of penetratin unbinding in a DMPC membrane from replica 6. The peptide is shown in new cartoon representation and the membrane is drawn in lines. The alpha carbon of residue 43 is shown as a van der Waals sphere to pinpoint the N-terminus. The aromatic residues (W48, F49 and W56) are drawn as orange licorice. (a) $t = 301.8$ ns; (b) $t = 306.3$ ns; (c) $t = 308.8$ ns; (d) $t = 310.3$ ns; (e) $t = 312.2$ ns; (f) $t = 312.9$ ns; (g) $t = 315.2$ ns; (h) $t = 324.1$ ns. Note that the box volume is changing significantly (see the edges represented as blue lines) because the replica is diffusing in temperature (the higher the temperature, the larger the area per lipid).

Penetratin insertion has a fluidising effect on membranes

Finally, we assessed the impact of penetratin insertion on lipids dynamics. The lipid order parameters for the *IN* and *OUT* systems, as well as those of some pure DMPC and pure DMPG membranes, are presented on Figure 8.

For the *IN* systems, the order parameter decreases when the peptide is added for both compositions, meaning that the membrane becomes more fluid. This result is in good agreement with some differential scanning calorimetry experiments (DSC), which present a weak fluidising effect at low peptide to lipid ratio (1/100)[29].

For the *OUT* systems, the situation is different according to the lipid composition. In *OUT*_{DMPG}, the order parameter is identical to that of a pure bilayer. In *OUT*_{DMPC}, the order parameter is in between the one of a pure bilayer and the one of the *IN*_{DMPC} system. These two results are not easy to explain since both *OUT* systems have not fully converged. All together, these analyses show that the full helical conformation has a larger effect on lipids than a disordered conformation.

NMR experiments reveal a weak helical state of penetratin in presence of POPC lipids

Our goal was to characterise by NMR the conformational space of penetratin and compare it with our MD simulations, most specifically in the two aqueous and zwitterionic lipid environments in which penetratin does not seem to adopt a stable folded state. The ¹H, ¹³C, ¹⁵N resonances of penetratin were assigned in aqueous solution (Table S3). These chemical shifts provide information on penetratin conformational propensities by examining their deviations from random coil values for each residue. Chemical shift analysis based on TALOS program confirmed that penetratin is disordered and does not have a stable secondary structure in solution. Nevertheless, residues 45 to 57 display weak negative deviations of their ¹H α chemical shifts from random coil values (average value of -0.10 ppm), which are indicative of some turn or helical propensity (Figure 9-A). This is also consistent with ¹³C α chemical shifts analysis (Figure S8), revealing weakly positive chemical shift deviations in the central 50-53 segment (average value of +0.4 ppm). The analysis of ¹H-¹H NOE correlation intensities shows that all residues display strong sequential H α _{*i*-1}/HN_{*i*} correlations and medium intra-residual H α _{*i*}-HN_{*i*} correlations, together with a few medium HN_{*i*-1}/HN_{*i*} sequential correlations, indicating that the peptide backbone mostly explores extended conformations. Noteworthy, a few *i*, *i*+2 to *i*, *i*+3 medium-range NOEs are observed at lower temperature (5°C), involving in particular the side-chain protons of I47/F49, I45/W48. These medium-range NOEs indicate that penetratin transiently explores helical turn conformations, in particular in the 45-49 segment rich in hydrophobic residues.

We next analysed the conformation of penetratin in the presence of zwitterionic lipid vesicles. As NMR studies are often restricted by the size of peptide/membrane complexes, we turned to small unilamellar vesicles as a membrane model. We chose POPC lipid for the NMR study rather than DMPC used in the MD simulations because of the higher stability of POPC SUVs. We checked by CD spectroscopy that penetratin exhibited the same random coil signature in both POPC and DMPC SUVs (Figure S9). The addition of POPC SUVs at a 1:25 peptide:lipid ratio had little effect on the 1D ¹H spectrum of penetratin (Figure S10): POPC lipid induced only marginal chemical shift variations and a slight broadening of resonances. This confirms that penetratin weakly interacts with zwitterionic lipids and that the NMR spectrum of penetratin is dominated by its major unbound state in solution. Interestingly, the 2D ¹H-¹H NOESY spectrum recorded in the presence of POPC lipids displays NOE peaks that were not observed in the absence of lipids. Such additional NOEs can be ascribed to an equilibrium between the major free form in solution and a minor lipid-bound form, which occurs on a fast exchange regime on the ¹H chemical shift NMR time scale. Therefore the analysis of these transferred NOEs from the membrane-bound to the free form yields information on the structure of the weakly populated, transient membrane-bound state. These NOEs consist in medium-range *i*, *i*+2 to *i*, *i*+4 correlations, which are observed throughout the sequence. In particular, the observation of medium-range H α -HN NOEs indicates the stabilisation of the backbone helical fold in the membrane-bound form. NOEs between side-chain protons prove the interaction between I45/W48, F49, I47/N51, W48/R52 side-chains in the 45-52 segment.

Figure 8: (A) Order parameter of DMPG lipids (B) or DMPC lipids without penetratin (black triangle), in the *OUT* systems (orange or light green triangle) and in the *IN* systems (red or dark green triangle). Only the *sn*-1 chains are considered.

Discussion

On the mechanism of insertion / folding within the membrane interface

The insertion / folding mechanism or partitioning / folding coupling of an AH with a membrane was described in three different stages in literature [56, 10]: i) attraction of the peptide thanks to electrostatic

Figure 9: (A) Chemical shift deviations (CSDs) from random coil values for $^1\text{H}\alpha$ protons of penetratin in water and in bicelles [33]; (B) intraresidual and sequential NOEs observed for penetratin in water at 20°C; (C) additional medium-range NOEs observed for penetratin in the presence of POPC SUVs at 20°C.

interactions, ii) insertion within the membrane/water interface in a random-coil conformation, iii) helix folding within this interface. Our T-REMD simulations do not allow us to address the global thermodynamic partitioning/folding coupling as described by White [10] because of a lack of convergence of the respective states. That is why we prefer to talk about insertion / folding mechanism rather than partitioning folding for what concerns the results described in this work.

However, our T-REMD simulations do give useful molecular insights on this insertion / folding mechanism. Indeed, while some replicas can be stuck in kinetic traps (inserted state with large hydrophobic residues deeply buried), some others follow a different behaviour (helix folding within the interface in DMPG, possible membrane unbinding in DMPC). Some phenomena such as the first stage of peptide diffusion towards the membrane are very well described: in DMPG this phase is very brief (less than 50

ns) thanks to favourable electrostatic interactions, while in DMPC it takes longer for all the replicas to fully insert (about 500 ns). Furthermore, the simulations unveil unexpected states, such as (weak) folded states in DMPC, which are confirmed by NMR. They also explain more complex phenomena such as the role of the IWF residues (see below).

T-REMD simulations follow the experimental trends

When comparing simulations and experiments, it is important to keep in mind the limitations due to the setup of the MD simulations. First, the amount of water in the simulations was chosen at about 40 water molecules per lipid. It is classical in membrane simulations since it provides full hydration to the membrane (i.e. it does not change the membrane property like in the case of dehydration), and at the same time the computational cost remains reasonable. However, the amount of water is several orders of magnitude higher in experiments: typically the water/lipid ratio is around 10,000 or even higher. Thus, the phase of peptide random diffusion in water is considerably shorter than what would happen in typical experiments. Second, in our simulations, the P/L ratio is 1/100 and only one peptide is simulated. Thus, it is not possible to observe phenomena such as dimerisation or cooperative associations such as toroidal pores. Last, we simulate only 100 lipids, which does not allow to observe membrane curvature, or penetratin-mediated liposome aggregation. For example, in the study of ref [29], the turbidity of penetratin / DMPG liposomes mixing increases. To infer the secondary structure of penetratin by CD, the authors had to heat at 60°C for two hours before measuring the spectrum. Despite these limitations, our simulations are well adapted when we focus on the conformational behaviour of the peptide. They represent diluted conditions for which peptide / peptide interactions can be neglected.

In Water, the mean helicity at 310 K in the second half of the simulation (once the overall helicity across all replicas has converged) is 22.1%. In the CD experiments at 25°C (298 K) of ref [29], no helicity was presented but the spectra were typical of random coil so the helical content is very weak. In our data recorded at 310 K in Water, a spectral deconvolution yields a helicity of about 10% [57]. It is difficult to infer if the residual helicity concerns some fully helical states, or only a part of the sequence which sometimes visit some helical conformation. Accordingly, the NMR chemical shift and NOE analysis show that penetratin does not adopt a stable alpha-helix in aqueous solution. However, the peptide does exhibit a helical propensity, as indicated by chemical shift analysis. Taking an overall average $^1\text{H}\alpha$ chemical shift deviation from random coil values of -0.38 ppm in proteins helices [58], the mean helicity of the 45-57 segment can be tentatively estimated to 20% at 303 K (mean chemical shift deviation of -0.08 ppm). The helical content marginally increases upon cooling (Figure S7) and reaches about 25% at 278 K (mean chemical shift deviation of -0.10 ppm). Thus, MD and NMR are in good agreement regarding the helicity in Water. Interestingly, the first MD cluster at 310 K (Figure S2) is stabilised by a long-range pi-pi interaction between F49 and W56.

In presence of lipids, it is more difficult to strictly compare the mean helicity between simulations and experiments. First, the T-REMD simulations have not fully converged (Figure S1) despite using μs trajectories (especially for the *OUT* systems). Second, it is difficult to assess exactly the amount of helix in the experiments. In DMPG, the CD experiments were obtained on conditions where some aggregation occur [29]. So it is difficult to infer how much of the signal has disappeared because of aggregation. We did encounter similar conditions when trying experiments with PG lipids (not shown). The NMR experiments which provided the structure [34] were done using bicelles with 10% only of PG lipids, which can lead to different helicity compared to DMPG LUV conditions. Based on the CSD of these experiments, we evaluate the helicity at about 40%. Last, in DMPC and POPC at 310 K, the CD spectrum is almost undistinguishable compared to that in Water. Likewise, the 1D ^1H NMR spectrum of penetratin in POPC SUVs and Water are also very similar. Both CD and NMR spectra are dominated by the major unstructured unbound states in water. Only the use of specific experiments such as transferred NOE can detect some weak helical states (see below). Despite these difficulties, the simulations clearly follow the experimental trends. For the *IN* systems, the helix disappears more rapidly in DMPC compared to DMPG. In the *OUT* systems, the fully helical state is very rare in DMPC, while it is more abundant and stable in DMPG. Furthermore, the simulations capture the right helix orientation in DMPG in terms of tilt angle: it is not perfectly horizontal, the N-term is more buried than the C-ter (Figure S4), which is in good agreement some NMR experiments [34].

A very interesting result revealed by our work is the presence of weak helical states in DMPC. Started from a peptide outside the bilayer, the *OUT*_{DMPC} system shows that in some very rare stages, some

alpha-helix spanning a major part of the peptide sequence could occur (yellow parts in Figure S6). However, they do not last long and the helix partitions less deeply than in DMPC. This is confirmed by our transferred NOE experiments that indeed present some characteristic NOEs of helical signature, mostly in the I45-R52 part of penetratin, and in the C-terminal 54-58 segment to a lesser extent. A similar strategy based on transferred NOE experiments has also been applied to a modified penetratin sequence [59] (with an Asp residue at the N-terminus). The authors identified helical states in the presence of LUVs of different lipid compositions, but vesicles made of purely zwitterionic lipids were not investigated.

Overall, our simulations show that the CHARMM36 and CHARMM36m force fields [42, 43] globally reproduce the experimental results. But what is really striking, is that they are even able to capture the tiny details such as the very weak helical state in DMPC. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time that some MD simulations describe this.

The IWF residues slow down the folding in DMPG and hold back the peptide within the membrane in DMPC

Penetratin has a peculiar sequence which is not highly amphipathic (Figure S4-C) with a modest hydrophobic moment of 0.327 (it can go up to 0.5 for strong amphipathic helices such as melittin, mastoparan [60]). This can be explained by R52 which lies on the hydrophobic face and I47 on the hydrophilic face. This explains the somehow weak helical content even in favourable conditions such as negatively charged lipids (DMPG), about 40%. Penetratin sequence has another peculiarity, the presence of three consecutive large hydrophobic residues, that is I47, W48 and F49 residues (that we call the IWF triad below). Beyond breaking penetratin amphipathicity, our simulations suggest that they play a prominent role in the interaction between penetratin and lipids.

In OUT_{DMPG} simulations, helix is slow to form because the peptide needs first to unfold in the interface. During this process, IWF triad will tend to insert deeply with the rest of the peptide unfolded (see Figure S5 when the black dots are below the phosphate level). This deep partitioning of IWF impairs helix folding. We believe it creates a supplementary free energy barrier for the following reason. These 3 residues have to go up (towards the water phase), away from their preferred position (deeply buried as if they were "alone"), and concomitantly the backbone has to undergo an important motion to form locally a helix, which is already very slow in the crowded phosphate environment (the most dense place in the bilayer). The deeply inserted IWF needs thus to be "pulled up", which acts as a supplementary kinetic barrier (which becomes a trap in our simulations), next to the classical slowed-down backbone motion of helix formation within the dense polar head environment. But then, once folded, the helix is stable.

In OUT_{DMPC} simulations, once the peptide has reached the bilayer, the IWF triad tends also to partition deeply in the hydrophobic core of the membrane (see Figure S6 when the black dots are below the phosphate level), as in DMPG. As described in results, this makes the unbinding a rare event at the time scale of our simulations. It explains why the peptide is so sticky with respect to the membrane. However, conversely to DMPG, when IWF leaves the core, the peptide very rarely fully folds in the interface (yellow in Figure S6). In the only three folding events we observed (yellow parts for replicas 7, 9 and 36), the folding occurred upper compared to DMPG (more towards the water phase). And also, the time it was folded was very short (in general < 150 ns) compared to DMPG (for example replica 26, the yellow colour remains more than 1000 ns).

In literature, the binding of large hydrophobic residues has already been observed as a first event of AH binding to a membrane [20, 55]. In the study of Vanni et al. [55], the insertion of large hydrophobic residues of the curvature sensor ALPS peptide in pre-existing packing defects was systematically observed. These latter are tiny spots where polar heads do not pack well [55]. In the study of Cui et al. [20], the binding of H0 peptide from BAR domain to a flat or negatively curved membrane started with the insertion of large hydrophobic residues the unfavourable, but then no folding occurred. The peptide was kinetically trapped and could not proceed towards folding. This was explained by a lack of packing defects. For the positively curved bilayer, where packing defects are more abundant, the authors could observe helix folding. In our case, we may be in an intermediate case: packing defects are probably not very abundant because we use DMPC and DMPG which have saturated aliphatic tails (which impair the formation of large packing defects [55]), but favourable electrostatic interactions come into play with DMPG lipids, and penetratin is not a curvature sensor, thus it may be slightly more favourable to folding than H0 [20] or ALPS [55] helices. Anyhow, the binding of large hydrophobic residues can become a

kinetic trap as what we observe in our work. In the future, it may be interesting to study in details helix folding vs packing defects for our penetratin/membrane systems.

Advantages and limitations of T-REMD for exploring AH / membrane interactions

In this work, we used T-REMD simulations as an enhanced sampling technique [44, 45]. T-REMD is a powerful technique where the sampling is enhanced by using high temperatures. The regular exchanges based on a Metropolis criterion allows the replicas to diffuse in temperature, while if we take all conformations at a given temperature, they follow a Boltzmann distribution. In this work, we applied it to the insertion / folding of penetratin. It is clearly an asset for accessing slow events such as interfacial helix folding. In this dense membrane environment, the friction is high thus classical MD simulations would not allow to observe folding. But on the other hand, our work also shows that if we start far from equilibrium, all replicas are very slow at converging (see Figure S1) even if some has reached the expected conformation. It is especially true for the OUT_{DMPG} system for which $2.3 \mu\text{s}$ per replica is not enough, only 6 replicas out of 38 has reached the helical state (Figure 4B). But even for the other systems, convergence has not yet been reached. For the OUT_{DMPG} system, starting from the NMR structure determined in SDS micelle was probably too helical. On the other hand, as no experimental structure in DMPG was available, it was the closest guess. For the IN_{DMPC} system, this starting helical state was even further from equilibrium, we thus expect the helical content to continue its decrease if we prolonged the simulations (Figure S1). One way to improve the sampling could be to mix the starting structures along the replicas. For example, in the IN systems, the even replicas could be started with the helical state, and the odd replicas with an extended state. This would accelerate the convergence. But even with this trick, T-REMD remains slow at converging.

In the rare studies that used T-REMD for peptide/membrane interactions, in the one Nymeyer on WALP16 insertion and folding, it is unclear whether their T-REMD has converged since at this time they used only 3.5 ns per replica (due to the limited computational power at that time). Here we used more than two orders of magnitude longer simulations and did not reach convergence.

Other enhanced sampling approaches have been used in literature. For example, high temperatures simulations have been used successfully to study melittin interfacial folding [22]. However, in this approach, it is important to ensure the thermostability of the AH, which is not guaranteed for penetratin compared to melittin. Moreover, one needs to extrapolate what happens at high temperatures to what would happen at low temperature. Metadynamics is another valuable technique for which one has to use collective variables. Cui et al. used the alpha-beta similarity along with the number of hydrogen bonds [20] for the study of H0 helix (from BAR domain) folding. The authors could compute a free energy of folding but only for the most favourable condition, which was the binding of the H0 helix to a positively curved membrane. This led to a converged PMF. For flat or negatively curved membranes, no converged PMF could be obtained. This suggests that this technique is appropriate for cases in which the insertion / folding is known to occur. Overall this illustrates that the different techniques have all pros and cons, and are thus complementary.

Conclusion

In this work, extensive T-REMD simulations and experiments have been used to probe the fine molecular mechanisms between the CPP penetratin and lipid membranes made of zwitterionic DMPC or anionic DMPG, as well as penetratin in Water. In this latter medium, there is a good agreement between MD and experiments with a helicity around 20%, which concerns the central residues, mainly the F49-N51 part. A possible interaction between F49 and W56 may play a stabilising role in this helical state. In lipids, although the T-REMD have not fully converged despite μs long simulations, they follow the right experimental trends. In DMPG, some replicas display a full insertion/folding process, and once folded the helix is stable. Experimentally, an analysis of the CSD from the published structure of penetratin [33] gives around 40% of helicity. Thus the T-REMD are compatible with a somehow moderate helicity in these conditions. In DMPC, the T-REMD present weaker interactions with possible unbinding events. But they also reveal some transient helical states which can be, at first, somehow of a surprise. Interestingly, some weak signals of helical states were confirmed by transferred NOE experiments. Next to this weak helical states, the peptide remains in unstructured conformations with the large hydrophobic residues buried in

the hydrophobic core of the membrane. This is again in good agreement with experiments. Our work also shows that the IWF residues plays a pivotal role in the interaction of penetratin with membranes. We propose they act as a kinetic trap by partitioning deeply in the membrane with the peptide in an unstructured conformation. In DMPG, it slows down helix formation, while in DMPC it slows down peptide unbinding from the membrane. Overall, our work shows that T-REMD and experiments are very complementary for understanding complex molecular details of peptide / membrane interactions. It also confirms the remarkable capacity of the CHARMM36 force field to predict reliable peptide / lipid interactions.

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Supplementary Information

Supplementary methods

T-REMD temperature

Systems	<i>Water</i>	<i>IN_{DMPC}</i>	<i>IN_{DMPG}</i>	<i>OUT_{DMPC}</i>	<i>OUT_{DMPG}</i>
	310.00	310.00	310.00	310.00	310.00
	312.82	312.44	312.46	312.44	312.46
	315.68	314.90	314.94	314.90	314.94
	318.55	317.38	317.44	317.38	317.44
	321.43	319.87	319.95	319.87	319.95
	324.34	322.37	322.47	322.37	322.47
	327.26	324.89	325.02	324.89	325.02
	330.21	327.43	327.57	327.43	327.57
	333.19	329.98	330.15	329.98	330.15
	336.18	332.55	332.74	332.55	332.74
	339.20	335.13	335.34	335.13	335.34
	342.24	337.73	337.96	337.73	337.96
	345.31	340.35	340.60	340.35	340.60
	348.39	342.98	343.25	342.98	343.25
	351.50	345.63	345.92	345.63	345.92
	354.63	348.29	348.61	348.29	348.61
	357.78	350.97	351.32	350.97	351.32
	360.96	353.67	354.04	353.67	354.04
Temperatures	364.16	356.38	356.78	356.38	356.78
(K)	367.38	359.11	359.53	359.11	359.53
	370.63	361.86	362.30	361.86	362.30
	373.90	364.62	365.09	364.62	365.09
	377.21	367.41	367.90	367.41	367.90
	380.53	370.20	370.72	370.20	370.72
	383.87	373.02	373.56	373.02	373.56
	387.25	375.85	376.42	375.85	376.42
	390.65	378.70	379.30	378.70	379.30
	394.07	381.56	382.19	381.56	382.19
	397.52	384.45	385.10	384.45	385.10
	401.00	387.35	388.03	387.35	388.03
	404.50	390.27	390.98	390.27	390.98
	408.02	393.21	393.95	393.21	393.95
	411.57	396.17	396.93	396.17	396.93
		399.14	399.94	399.14	399.94
		402.14	402.96	402.14	402.96
		405.15	406.00	405.15	406.00
		408.18	409.06	408.18	409.06
		411.23	412.14	411.23	412.00

Table S1: Temperature of each replica for the 5 T-REMD simulations presented.

Supplementary figures and tables

Figure S1: Mean helicity averaged over all replicas for each T-REMD.

Figure S2: Penetratin representative structure in Water. This structure was obtained by clustering all the conformations at 310K between 250 and 500 ns. It is the first cluster representing xxx% of all the conformations of that part. The peptide is represented in cyan ribbon, each amino acid is represented in lines and coloured by atom type and the carbon α of the Nter and Cter are labelled.

Figure S3: Helicity per residue at 310 K for the (A) *Water* system, (B) IN_{DMPG} system and (C) IN_{DMPC} . Their respective mean helicity at 310 K is 22.07%, 70.02% and 61.38%

Replica	Time	Observation
5	~1 ns ~ 134 ns ~ 140 to ~ 800 ns ~ 833 ns ~ 1 000 ns	Nter enters the DMPG bilayer W48 and F49 enter the bilayer W56 enters and leaves the bilayer W56 enters the bilayer and add 1 helix turn Penetratin in full helix
18	~1 ns ~ 6 ns ~ 140 to ~ 800 ns 1 419 ns 1 456 ns 1 569 ns 2 052 ns 2 059 ns	Nter enters the DMPG bilayer W48 and F49 enter the bilayer W56 enters and leaves the bilayer Penetratin in full helix W56 enters the bilayer W56 leaves the bilayer and loose helix in Cter Penetratin in full helix W56 enters the bilayer
19	~4 ns ~ 24 ns 30 ns 40 ns ~204 ns ~410 ns 602 ns	Nter enters the DMPG bilayer W48 and F49 enter the bilayer, lose of helicity F49 leaves the bilayer, add 1 helix turn F49 enters the bilayer Add 1 helix turn W56 enters the bilayer, add 1 helix turn Penetratin in full helix
26	5 ns ~327 ns ~329 ns ~1 101 ns ~1 109 ns ~1 250 ns ~1 413 ns ~1 484 ns	Nter enters the DMPG bilayer - helix on the wrong side Total lose of helicity, W48 enters the bilayer F49 enters the bilayer, add 1 helix turn W56 enters the bilayer, add 1 helix turn Penetratin in full helix W56 leaves the bilayer, lose of helicity W56 enters the bilayer, gain helicity Penetratin in full helix
34	~4 ns ~10 ns ~12 ns	Nter and W48 enter the DMPG bilayer W56 enters the bilayer F49 enters the bilayer

Table S2: Timestamps for the 5 replicas where penetratin folds in OUT_{DMPG} system.

Figure S4: Partitioning of penetratin amino-acids for the (A) *OUT_{DMPG}* or (B) *OUT_{DMPC}* system at 310 K. The membrane is represented by the mean position of its phosphates as well as its C₂ atom (first hydrophobic atom of the *sn*-2 chain [check this]). Amino-acids are colour coded according to their nature: positively charged residues are in blue, hydrophobic residues are in yellow and polar uncharged residues are in pink. The analysis was performed on the conformations between 500 and 1 000 ns at 310 K for *OUT_{DMPC}* and between 500 and 2 374 ns for *OUT_{DMPG}*. (C) The helical wheel of penetratin generated by heliquest, its hydrophobic moment is 0.327 [61].

Figure S5: Position of penetratin center of mass (COM) and of the phosphate of each leaflet in the OUT_{DMPG} system. The COM is coloured by helicity throughout the simulation.

Figure S6: Position of penetratin center of mass (COM) and of the phosphate of each leaflet in the OUT_{DMPC} system. The COM is coloured by helicity throughout the simulation.

Figure S7: Chemical shift deviations (CSDs) from random coil values for $^1\text{H}\alpha$ protons of penetratin in water at 3 different temperatures (5, 20 and 30°C).

Figure S8: Chemical shift deviations (CSDs) from random coil values for $^{13}\text{C}\alpha$ protons of penetratin in water at 2 different temperatures (5°C and 30°C).

Figure S9: CD spectra of penetratin in aqueous and lipid SUV environments at different lipid/peptide (L/P) ratios.

Figure S10: 1D ¹H NMR spectra (600 MHz, 30°C) of penetratin in aqueous (blue) and POPC SUVs (red).

Residue	¹⁵ N	¹ HN	¹³ C _α	¹ H _α	¹³ C _β	¹ H _β	Other side chain resonances
Arg43	n.d.	n.d.	55.8	3.92	31.7	1.86	Cγ 26.4 Hγ 1.61 Cδ 43.4 Hδ 3.19
Gln44	n.d.	n.d.	55.9	4.42	29.7	1.99, 2.04	Cγ 33.9 Hγ 2.35 Nε2 112.5 Hε2 7.57, 6.86
Ile45	123.9	8.36	61.1	4.15	38.9	1.82	Cγ1 27.3 Hγ1 1.45, 1.17 Cγ2 17.5 Hγ2 0.86 Cδ1 12.9 Hδ1 0.85
Lys46	125.9	8.32	56.3	4.27	33.1	1.61	Cγ 24.8 Hγ 1.19, 1.27 Cδ 29.1 Hδ 1.56 Cε 42.1 Hε 2.81
Ile47	122.5	8.03	61.0	4.11	38.9	1.73	Cγ1 27.3 Hγ1 1.36, 1.09 Cγ2 17.6 Hγ2 0.72 Cδ1 12.8 Hδ1 0.80
Trp48	125.2	8.12	57.3	4.63	29.9	3.16	Cδ1 127.3 Hδ1 7.16 Nε1 129.5 Hε1 10.12 Cε3 120.9 Hε3 7.55 Cζ2 114.7 Hζ2 7.49 Cζ3 122.1 Hζ3 7.12 Cη2 124.6 Hη2 7.23
Phe49	121.7	7.94	57.7	4.50	39.8	2.90, 3.00	Cδ 131.9 Hδ 7.15 Cε 131.5 Hε 7.33 Cζ 130.0 Hζ 7.29
Gln50	n.d.	8.14	56.3	4.13	29.4	1.88, 1.98	Cγ 33.8 Hγ 2.21 Nε2 112.0 Hε2 7.41, 6.83
Asn51	n.d.	n.d.	53.5	4.61	38.8	2.77, 2.85	Nδ2 112.6 Hδ2 7.60, 6.91
Arg52	n.d.	8.24	56.6	4.25	30.7	1.74, 1.83	Cγ 27.2 Hγ 1.59 Cδ 43.4 Hδ 3.11
Arg53	121.3	8.28	56.3	4.25	30.6	1.74, 1.81	Cγ 27.3 Hγ 1.58 Hδ 3.13
Met54	121.2	8.20	55.5	4.38	33.0	1.9	Cγ 32.1 Hγ 2.44, 2.49 Cε 17.1 Hε 2.05
Lys55	n.d.	8.19	56.4	4.25	33.0	1.63, 1.70	Cγ 24.8 Hγ 1.32, 1.37 Cδ 29.2 Hδ 1.63 Hε 2.92 Cδ1 127.3 Hδ1 7.24 Nε1 129.5 Hε1 10.14
Trp56	122.1	8.05	57.2	4.67	29.9	3.24	Cε3 121.1 Hε3 7.59 Hζ2 7.49 Cζ3 122.1 Hζ3 7.14 Cη2 124.7 Hη2 7.24
Lys57	123.4	7.99	56.1	4.22	33.5	1.60, 1.72	Cγ 24.6 Hγ 1.26 Cδ 29.2 Hδ 1.60 Cε 42.0 Hε 2.93
Lys58	123.5	8.11	56.4	4.12	33.1	1.68, 1.78	Cγ 24.9 Hγ 1.40 Cδ 29.3 Hδ 1.68 Cε 42.2 Hε 2.98 NH ₂ 108.8 H ₂ N 7.57, 7.07

Table S3: ¹⁵N, ¹³C, ¹H NMR assignments of penetratin in water at 30°C.